

An Islamic Overview of Political Party Membership and National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract

In every country where democracy is practiced, political parties possess the basic roles of presenting and promoting credible candidates for elections. Beside this, they steer and monitor the candidates through their regimes and propel them to deliver good governance base on parties' manifestoes. This functions when fully discharged is a good recipe for development and national integration. This paper has however revealed a dismal performance of political parties in Nigeria with regard to their basic functions. This paper therefore idealizes the position of Islam on political party membership with a view to converse for progressive politicking and promotion of national integration in Nigeria. The paper showcases that Islam is not averse to political party membership but discourages dearth of political ideology; emergence of non-credible candidates and failure of political parties to monitor their members who occupy elective and appointive positions. The paper recommends among others that the righteous and most credible members should be assisted and presented to represent political parties in general elections and that political parties should be empowered to monitor and sanction their representatives who fail to deliver good governance.

Keywords: Political party, Islam, membership, election, national integration

Introduction

Political parties are generally known as entities that organize competitions for political offices. This is because members of political parties contest elections under a shared label. Political parties are the entire apparatus that supports the election of a group of candidates. According to Adams, a political party is a durable organization united by common principles which "has for its immediate end the advancement of the interests and the realization of the ideals of the particular group or groups which it represents."¹

The formation of large groups or factions to advocate for their shared interests is an ancient practice. Plato mentions the political factions of Classical Athens in the *Republic* and Aristotle discusses the tendency of different types of government to produce factions in the *Politics*. Instances of recorded political groups or factions in history also included the late Roman Republic's *Populares* and *Optimates* factions as well as the Dutch Republic's *Orangists* and the *Staatsgezinde*.² Among the pre-Islamic Arabs, chiefdom was not hereditary but elective. Their practice was such in which all the members participate in choosing a leader. In all these arrangements however, elections typically featured a much lower level of competition, and instead of adopting the machinery of political parties, they were dominated by individual networks or cliques that could independently propel a candidate to victory in an election.³

A hint of party influence is however established in the election of the first Caliph who ruled after the death of Prophet Muhammad. The fact that the Prophet did not appoint a successor to rule after him paved way for some Muslims to organize themselves into parties and indicated their interest in the Caliphate. They even nominated and supported candidates of their choice. These parties and their candidates include: The Muhajirun (emigrants), the Ansar (Helpers) and Ashabu n Nass wa ta'yin' (the legitimist). Each of these parties was reported to have alluded reasons for their choice. In a meeting conveyed by the Chief Companion of the Prophet, their representative conversed for their candidates by citing their merits and qualities. After a long deliberation, the general opinion favoured Abu Bakr and he was elected as the first Caliph.⁴ This was a significant innovation in an Era when monarchical system prevailed and leaders were never actually elected.

The first modern political parties developed in early modern Britain in the 18th century after the exclusion crisis and the glorious revolution. The *Whig* faction organized itself around support for Protestant constitutional monarchy as opposed to absolute rule. Whereas the conservative faction supported a strong monarchy, and these two groups competed in the politics of the United Kingdom throughout the 18th century. The Rockingham Whigs have in fact been identified as the first modern political party, because they retained a coherent party label and motivating principles even while out of power.⁵ At the end of 18th century, the United States also developed a party system, called the First Party System. Although the framers of the 1787 United States Constitution did not all anticipate that American political disputes would be primarily organized around political parties, political controversies in the early 1790s over the extent of federal government powers saw the emergence of two proto-political parties, the Federalist Party and the Democratic-Republican Party.⁶

By the early 19th century, a number of countries had developed stable modern party systems. The party system that developed in Sweden has been called the world's first party system, on the basis that previous party systems were not fully stable or institutionalized. In many European countries, including Belgium, Switzerland, Germany, and France, political parties organized around a liberal-conservative divide, or around religious disputes. The spread of the party model of politics was however accelerated by the 1848 Revolutions around Europe.⁷ This however presents a remarkable difference from what obtained in other political climates. During the wave of decolonization in the mid-20th century, many newly sovereign countries outside of Europe and North America developed party systems that often emerged from their movements for independence. For example, a system of political parties arose out of factions in the Indian independence movement, and was strengthened and stabilized by the policies of Indira Gandhi in the 1970s. The formation of the Indian National Congress, which developed in the early 20th century as a pro-independence faction in British India and immediately became a major political party after Indian independence, foreshadowed the dynamic in many newly independent countries; for example, the Uganda National Congress was a pro-independence party and the first political party in Uganda, and its name was chosen as an homage to the Indian National Congress.⁸

In Nigeria, the earliest political parties were formed in 1959, shortly before Nigeria gained independence. The three political parties were the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC) which was led by Nnamdi Azikiwe. The second political party was the northern people's congress (NPC) which was led by Ahmadu Bello. The third one was the Action Group which was led by Obafemi Awolowo. The three parties gained control in the East, North and West respectively. Besides these earliest experiments, the Social Democratic Party (SDP) and National Republican Party (NRP) were formed in 1993 under the military regime which had ruled since 1983. The achievement of these parties was however punctured by the annulment of June 12 Presidential election which was won by Chief M.K.O. Abiola. However, since the return of civilian rule in 1999, politicians have been elected under the banners of political parties such as the People's Democratic Party (PDP), Action Congress (AC), Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), All Progressive Congress (APC), the All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA), Labour Party (LP) and many other political parties.⁹ All this account therefore indicates a broader suffrage rights and eventually universal suffrage have been embraced throughout democracies. Political parties have expanded dramatically, and political parties have gained ground as intermediaries between the public and the government. And they have remained the generally acknowledged machinery of presenting candidates for election.

Basic Elements of Political Parties

Political parties are often structured in similar ways across countries. They typically feature a single party leader, a group of party executives, and a community of party members¹⁰. In countries with large sub-national regions, particularly federalist countries, there may be regional party leaders and regional party members in addition to the national membership and leadership. This has in fact remained the practice in Nigeria. Every political party also generally uphold peculiar ideology. Political ideologies are one of the major organizing features of political parties, and parties often officially align themselves with specific ideologies.

Parties adopt ideologies for a number of reasons. Ideological affiliations for political parties send signals about the types of policies they might pursue if they were in power. Ideologies also differentiate parties from one another so that voters can select the party that advances the policies that they most prefer.¹¹ A party may thus seek to advance an ideology by convincing voters to vote for its candidates.

He further asserts that common ideologies that can form a central part of the identity of a political party include liberalism, conservatism, socialism, communism, anarchism, fascism, feminism, environmentalism, nationalism, fundamentalism, Islamism, and multiculturalism. Liberalism is the ideology that is most closely connected to the history of democracies and is often considered to be the dominant or default ideology of governing parties in much of the contemporary world. Though ideologies are central to a large number of political parties around the world, not all political parties have an organizing ideology, or exist to promote ideological policies. For example, some political parties may be clientelist or patronage-based organizations, which are largely concerned with distributing goods. Other political parties may be created as tools for the advancement of an individual politician. It is also common, in countries with important social cleavages along ethnic or racial lines, to represent the interests of one ethnic group or another. This may involve a non-ideological attachment to the interests of that group, or may be a commitment based on an ideology like identity politics. While any of these types of parties may be ideological, there are political parties that do not have any organizing ideology.¹²

Funding of Political Parties

Common sources of party funding across countries include dues paid by party members, advocacy groups and lobbying organizations, corporations, trade unions, and candidates who may self-fund activities. In most countries, government also provides some level of funding for political parties. Nearly all of the 180 countries examined by the International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance have some form of public funding for political parties, and about a third have regular payments of government funds that goes beyond campaign reimbursements¹³. In some countries, public funding for parties depends on the size of that party: for example, a country may only provide funding to parties which have more than a certain number of candidates or supporters. A common argument for public funding of political parties is that it creates fairer and more democratic elections by enabling more groups to compete, whereas many advocates of private funding of parties argue that donations to parties are a form of political expression that should be protected in a democracy. They postulate that public financing of political parties may decrease parties' pursuit of funds through corrupt methods, by decreasing their incentive to find alternate sources of funding.¹⁴

Having secured the required funds, parties may deploy money in order to secure better electoral outcomes. Parties often spend money to train activists, recruit volunteers, create and deploy advertisements, conduct research and support for their leadership in between elections, and promote their policy agenda. Many political parties and candidates across the world engage in a practice called clientelism, in which they distribute material rewards to people in exchange for political support. Despite a general declaration of this practice as being illegal, it is nevertheless a widespread phenomenon. Some members of political parties even engage directly in vote buying, in which they give money to voters in exchange for their vote.¹⁵

In order to curtail the abuses associated with funding, fundraising and expenditures by political parties are typically regulated by governments, with many countries' regulations focusing on who can contribute money to parties; how parties' money can be spent; and how much of it can pass through the hands of a political party. Two main ways in which regulations affect parties are by intervening in their sources of income and by mandating that they maintain some level of transparency about their funding. One common type of restriction on how parties acquire money is to limit who can donate money to political parties; for example, people who are not citizens of a country may not be allowed to make contributions to that country's political parties, in order to prevent foreign interference. It is also common to limit how much money an individual can give to a political party in each election. Similarly, many governments cap the total amount of money that can be spent by each

party in an election. Transparency regulations may require parties to disclose detailed financial information to the government, and in many countries, transparency laws require those disclosures to be available to the public, as a safeguard against potential corruption. None the less, political parties deserve to be properly funded to enable them discharge their functions to the public. In Nigeria for example, political parties were formed to perform the following roles: Sponsorship of candidates for electoral offices; conducting party primaries to select candidates; establishing the rules and regulation for internal party politics; conducting voter education and enlightenment on party politics; conducting electoral campaigns during elections; funding electoral campaigns; effective representation of diverse interests and inclusive participation in democratic governance, and formation of government upon winning of an election.¹⁶ The effective discharge of these functions is the essence of any democratic government. And by fulfilling the above tasks, political parties in Nigeria will perform their role as the cornerstone of democratic society. It will also give them the wherewithal to overcome most of their challenges.

Challenges Facing Political Parties in Nigeria

It has been observed that registration for membership of political parties in Nigeria is not usually done with utmost feeling of patriotism. Party cards are carried by most members who are totally oblivious of the party's programme, policy and manifesto. Political parties in Nigeria have not actually portray the right qualities in the conventional sense; they have been described as open-door, special purpose vehicle where members, just like passengers embark and disembark at will.¹⁷ Membership of political parties has been used as the surest means of accessing state resources since winners usually take all. Discussions at political meetings have fallen short of its purpose. Most members merely attend meetings to lobby for 'pay-outs' and positions. Debates are usually centered on elected or appointed officials who have not shown up to share the largess of office as well as formulas for sharing cash or other forms of inducement from new aspirants. At the ward level, members are sometimes enticed with two cups of beans or rice from donors who wish to contest elections.

The inclination towards money-politics is another problem hindering effective functioning of political parties in Nigeria. The challenge of financial wherewithal to contest elective positions often rule out credible aspirants among members of political parties This is a factor constituting serious impediment to political participation and it is one of the reason for widespread corruption among elected officials. Campaign activities which are often championed by political parties in Nigeria often usher in a season of fear for common Nigerians. This is usually occasioned by the heinous crimes that are perpetrated by political actors in their efforts to win elections by all means. Some of the unethical practices in the Nigerian political campaign include vilification of political opponents, physical violence and assault, use of thugs to canvass for the support of the electorates. Aniekwe and Kushie capture this phenomenon in these words, "...the Nigerian general elections have always been a cause for concern. It has always been marred with series of anomalies. There are always complaints and obvious cases of violence, vote buying, rigging, and other electoral vices which are often perpetrated and sponsored by members of political parties who see themselves as above the laws of the land."¹⁸

Political parties in Nigeria also engage in party politics. Party Politics in this context refers to the activities of political parties in the course of capturing state power and in exercising that power through the formation and implementation of public policy as initiated and executed by political actors (politicians) which direct the affairs of political parties.¹⁹ The winner-take-all syndrome also aggravate desperate moves by political contenders. And performance have remained low due to their lack of or non -implementation of progressive policies by political office holders. They generally fail in the provision of a better education and other critical infrastructures. This has created porous society and political erosion which has given birth to insurgencies, social unrest and ethnic militias. This and among others have served as a barrier to national integration and development in Nigeria. It is therefore noteworthy that political parties due to their far-reaching influence on elected officials have a role to play in the establishment of good governance. This study idealizes the Islamic viewpoints in this regard.

Islamic Views on Membership of Political Parties

Islam is not averse to membership of political parties in a secular democracy, but rather, it provides a regulatory framework to make such participation acceptable in its purview. The position of Islam is embedded in the Quran where Allah emphasizes that all Prophets led by good example, managed their societies, encouraged what was good and discouraged what was bad (Qur'an 21:73).

Islam attaches importance to leadership to the extent that no matter how small the number of Muslims in any given situation may be, be it on a journey or a gathering, a leader must be appointed, who must be of the best of them in terms of spiritual disposition, character and leadership capacity. A submits that the Prophet (SAW) instructed that Muslims should ensure leadership among them whenever they are up to three in a given community²⁰. It is clear from the foregoing that membership of political party with the aim of electing credible leaders is a compulsory duty as far as Islam is concerned. It is an obligatory task required for the good of every society. An important Islamic concept concerning the formation of parties which promote election of leaders is the *shura* (consultation) with people regarding their affairs. (Qur'an 3:153 and Qur'an 42:36). The standard Arabian practice during the early caliphates was for the prominent men of a kinship group, or tribe, to gather after a leader's death and elect a leader from amongst themselves, although there was no specified procedure for this *shura*, or consultative assembly. Candidates were usually from the same lineage as the deceased leader but they were not necessarily his sons. Capable men who would lead well were preferred over an ineffectual direct heir, as there was no basis in the majority Sunnī view that the head of state or governor should be chosen based on lineage alone. Decision-making power vested with a council (*shura*) of notable and trusted companions of Muhammad (*ṣaḥāba*) and representatives of different Arab tribes (most of them selected or elected within their tribes). Traditional Sunnī Muslim jurists agree that the *shura*, loosely translated as "consultation", is a function of the Islamic caliphate and the *Majlis-ash-Shura* serve as advisers to the caliph.²¹ The importance of this is premised on the following verses of the Quran: "...those who answer the call of their Lord and establish the prayer, and who conduct their affairs by Shura are loved by God (Qur'an 42:48) consult them (the people) in their affairs. Then when you have taken a decision (from them), put your trust in Allah" (3:159).

The *Majlis* were responsible for the election of a new Caliph. Al-Mawardi wrote that members of the *Majlis* should satisfy three conditions: they must be just, they must have enough knowledge to distinguish a good caliph from a bad one, and must have sufficient wisdom and judgment to select the best Caliph. Al-Mawardi also stated that in case of emergencies when there is no caliphate and no *Majlis*, the people themselves should institute a council of *Majlis*, select a list of candidates for the role of Caliph, then the *Majlis* should select from the list of candidates.²² Question could however be raised about the similarity of *Shurah* and political party arrangement in the modern democracy. The advocates of democratic ideas among Muslim scholars often canvas that Islam can play a public role within a democratic system by supporting democratic procedures such as party membership, participation in elections while offering religious or moral objections toward some aspects of Western democracy seen as incompatible with Sharia. This position has been exemplified by Islamic scholar like Yusuf. He further asserts that rather than sticking to belief that democracy requires restricting religion to private life, Muslims are duty-bound to offer a political model where democratic institutions and values can coexist with the values and principles of *sharia*. Islamic view thus stresses the concepts of *Maslaha* (public interest), *ʿAdl* (justice), *Islah* (the principle of reformation) and *Shura*. Muslims in leadership positions are expected to uphold justice and promote good governance. As members of political parties, they are also required to personify these virtues.²³

A demonstration of ideal political party membership could also be inferred from historical events which took place after the passage of Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.). Ayoob submits that after the death of Muhammad (S.A.W.) in 632 CE, his community needed to appoint a new leader, giving rise to the title of *caliph* and a series of four caliphs governed the early Islamic empire: Abū Bakr (632–634), ʿUmar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb (Umar I, 634–644), ʿUthmān ibn ʿAffān (644–656), and ʿAlī ibn Abī Ṭālib (656–661). These leaders are known as the *rāshidūn* (rightly-guided) Caliphs. Although the suffrage was limited, they were all elected to

govern the Muslims. With regard to party membership as an instrument of electing leaders, he further asserts that the election of Abu Bakr is quite significant. The three parties that emerged – the *Muhajirun*, the *Ansar*, *Ashabu 'n – Nass wa ta'yin* had their manifestoes. They canvassed for their candidates by projecting their qualities and merits rather than echoing the faults of their opponents²⁴.

For example, the *Muhajirun* (emigrants) based their claim on having belonged to the tribe of the Prophet and of course the first group of people to accept Islam. The merits of their candidate, Abu Bakr as particularly projected include the following: He was an elderly man who possess the required knowledge and wisdom to govern the Muslims. He was the most senior companion of the Prophet. He was from the Quraysh tribe. He was the most bosom friend and companion to the Prophet. A reference to these facts was cited in Quran 9:40 and the Prophet had appointed him to deputize for him when he was sick (Yusof,2013).

On the other hand, the *Ansar at Medinah* claimed a right to the Caliphate. They cited their generosity towards the Prophet and the *Muhajirun*. They opined that if they did not give Muhammad and other Muslims the needed asylum, both would have perished and gone into oblivion. And that their contribution to the survival of Islam gave them an edge over all other contenders.

The third party are the 'legitimists' (*Ashabu n - Nass wa ta'yin*) who reasoned that Allah and his Apostle could not have left the *Ummah* of believers to the whims of an electorate and that someone must have been designated to succeed the Prophet. They therefore held that the only person designated was Ali bn Abi Talib the paternal cousin of the Prophet, the husband of his only surviving daughter and one of the first three believers. Aside from projecting the qualities of their candidates, historical accounts also revealed that the *Muhajirun* and *Ansar* formed a coalition of *Shahabah* (Companions) and stood behind Abu Bakr who emerged as the first Caliph through a "voice votes."²⁵ This incidence was quite spectacular in an era when appointment of rulers across the world was hereditary.

The process of electing the first Caliph of Islam, therefore portend great lessons for modern day democracy. The parties as shown were established to project the qualities of their candidates which aligned with the ideology of *Umah* (Muslim Community) at that time. The meetings and deliberations of the parties were not focused on achieving selfish interest, the parties engaged one another in an atmosphere of decorum and the most popular opinion prevailed. It could therefore be inferred from the foregoing that Islam is not opposed to political party membership as an instrument of electing leaders. This notwithstanding, Muslims need to consider the ideological position of political parties; their resolution and focus on election of righteous candidates; and their policy of monitoring the performance of their elected or appointed members as a pre-requisite for political party membership in Nigeria. Each of these positions as established in the all-encompassing codes of Islam are discussed as follows:

Ideology of Political Party and purpose of membership

Based on the perspective of Islam, leaders and other member of political parties are required to adhere strictly to the rules of moral responsibility in spiritual and social endeavours. The powers of leadership and the qualification to join the league of selectors of leaders only rest on the righteous people. The Qur'an 24:55 points to this thus: "Allah had promised those of you who behave and do good that he will most certainly make them His vicegerent on the earth." Therefore, every political party must uphold an ideology which focuses on promoting good governance and eschew all inclination to self-service and corruption in the society. People who subscribe to this ideology will thus be able to join hands to promote election of good leaders in the society.

Election and Promotion of Righteous Candidates for Election

It has been established that no ideological position can work in the hands of those who do not subscribe to its principles (Qura'n 3:118, 9:16), the members of political party should elect candidate whose track records indicates that he is honest, trustworthy, God fearing and virtuous (Q4:58). Beside this, such candidates should be well educated, wise, intelligent and physically fit to bear the rigour of administration. (Qura'n 2:124, 26:151-

152). Members are also duty-bound to eschew all forms of corruption or inducement during primary election. A high level of transparency should be maintained in order to elect the most credible candidates.

Monitoring of Elected Members and Political Appointees

The Quran is quite explicit about the role of leaders in all societies. In this context, leaders and members of political parties need to be empowered to act as watch dogs and monitors of their candidates who have been elected or appointed into government. They should be empowered to censor such officials if they fail to address the main purpose of governance which include:

- i. Establishment of justice and equity in people's affairs (Qura'n 52: 25)
- ii. Harnessing the powers and resources of the state for people's welfare and eradication of corruption and evils in the society (Qura'n 22:41).

A demonstration of acceptability of this role is found in the inaugural speech of Abu Bakr upon his election and the first Caliph of Islam. When the teeming crowd paid allegiance to him, he addressed them as follows: "You have elected me your Kahlifa though I am not better than you. I need your advice and help. If I do right, help me. If I do wrong correct me. In my sight the powerful and the weak are alike and to both I wish to render justice. You should obey me as long as I obey God and his Prophet. If I disobey them, you should forsake me." This address was not empty promises as historical evidence actually shows that he lived up to the pledge.²⁶

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the foregoing, it could be asserted that membership of political parties is not a taboo for Muslims, but like other things which a Muslim engages in, whether socially, economically, professionally or politically; it must be conceived as worship to attain the pleasure of Allah. Base on this, one is obliged to make the following recommendations: (1). Muslims who are members of political parties should strive to adopt the principles of justice and welfare of the governed as prescribed by Islam (2). Political parties in Nigeria should endeavour to strengthen internal democratic principles. (3). The best and righteous people should be assisted and presented to represent the parties in general election and (4). When campaigning for election, political parties should avoid language of abuse, hate speech and libelous expressions against opponents. In addition to this, political parties should be required to establish policies, rules and regulations aimed at deterring candidates, party members and agents from participating or encouraging electoral offences.

Members of political parties should engage citizens in identifying their concerns and develop party policies and manifestos that respond to citizens' priorities. Currently, elections in Nigeria expose the deep rifts that exist between tribes, regions and religions because political leaders are unable to conduct issue-based election campaigns as well as deliver on their promises. Parties should also play the essential role of providing oversight for elected party members as well as those appointed to political offices. This will promote transparency and accountability in government processes and policies. By monitoring the implementation of their manifestos, political parties would encourage their elected members to project the party's principles and promote good governance.

The electoral management body and political parties should, as part of their statutory functions, carry out regular sensitization programmes and conduct events to identify and discuss the myriads of problems bedeviling political parties with a view to finding solutions to them. And on a final note best practices that buttress selfless services to the entire citizens should be encouraged in the act of party politics in the country. There is a need for active political engagement and aggressive political education to sensitize the masses on the essence of electing responsible and reliable citizens to political offices.

Endnotes

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